

Growth and Production of Jack Bean in Npk Fertilization and Probiotic Bacteria Applications

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Abstract

This research aims to increase the growth and production of jack beans through the provision of NPK fertilizer and probiotic microbes, carried out from September 2017 to July 2018 at the Cikarawang Experimental Garden, IPB University, and various types of laboratory analysis until August 2018, and designed in a complete randomized block with nine treatments fertilization, and three replications. Experimental plot measuring 400 x 550 cm with 56 plant populations (double row planting pattern 50 x 50 x 100 cm) and 12 sample plants. 5 sample plants were used for growth analysis (relative growth rate and leaf area index) planted in polybags. The treatment did not affect the generative growth and analysis of plant growth but affected most of the yield and production components. Treatment of organic and bio-organic fertilizers followed by probiotic solutions tended to be better and not different from 100% NPK. The treatment has not been able to increase pod harvest (10.9 pods) and production. Rotten pods, empty pods, and deciduous pods were still high (11.9 pods), and there were easy pods (8.9 pods). The treatment causes changes in aggregate in the soil texture but does not cause changes in soil classification

Keywords: NPK fertilization, bio-organic, probiotic bacteria

Introduction

Canavalia ensiformis L. is a type of sword bean from the *Fabaceae* family with a white seed coat. This plant has an erect type of growth, and the height can reach more than two meters. Jack bean has a long harvest age, and harvest period thus this plant is more suitable for cultivation in areas with a long dry season. The harvest period is during the rainy season, will cause the rot of the pods and eventually lead to crop failure.

According to Windarti et al., 2010 jack beans contain 37,57 - 37,65% protein, 4,45 - 4,53 % fat, and 36,31 - 37,27 % starch; mean while according to Rani et al., 2013 the protein and fat content in jack beans are higher than soybean flour, namely protein 28,98 - 34,30%, and fat 24,72 - 29,85%. The production of jack bean is also higher than soybeans, which is around 1,7 - 3,5 tons ha⁻¹ (e.g. Sarijan et al., 2019; Sunaryo Y dan Prasetyowati SE, 2022). Jack bean can be used to make a variety of foods, and one of them is to make tempeh instead of soybeans (e.g. Kustyawati et al., 2017; Andriani et al., 2018).

Jack bean production has not reached optimal results due to the occurrence of very high flower fall. According to Nazir 2016, 'the number of pods that fell on the sword bean plant was related to the insufficiency of photosynthate for embryo development. The fall of the flowers and pods can be caused by various causes, one of which is the limited available nutrients for plants, especially in the generative growth phase. The length of the harvest period for sword beans with an indeterminate type of growth can cause nutrient deficiencies and eventually lead to the fall of flowers and pods formed in the final phase.

In the soil and free air, there is a source of nutrients for plant growth, but sometimes the presence is not available so it cannot be utilized by plants. The use of microbes as symbiotic organisms or as solvents can be a solution so that plant nutrients found in nature can be utilized by plants. The use of symbiotic microbes and mineral solvents is also expected to be an alternative to avoid environmental damage and water

pollution due to the use of uncontrolled chemical fertilizers. In general, this study aims to increase the growth and production of sword beans while the specific goal is to obtain the right pair of probiotic microbes as biological fertilizers for sword beans.

Materials and Methods

Plant material and research methods

The research was conducted from September 2017 to August 2018, located in the Cikarawang experimental garden at Bogor Agricultural University. The materials used were jack bean seeds harvested in October 2016, cow manure, urea, TSP and KCl fertilizer, systemic herbicide with active ingredient isopropyl amine glyphosate (glyphosate-isopropyl ammonium) 486 g l^{-1} , a pesticide with active ingredient deltamethrin 25 g l^{-1} , as well as a fungicide with the active ingredient Mankozeb 80 WP. The tools used are land clearing and processing tools, pruning shears, plant supports, markers, hand sprayers, scales, germination tubs, drawing tools, writing instruments, data processing tools, and other equipment.

The study was designed in a Randomized Block Design (RBD) which consisted of nine treatments and three replications to obtain 27 experimental units. The fertilization treatment consists of:

P1 = without fertilization.

P2 = fertilization 50 kg Urea, 100 kg TSP and 112.5 kg KCL (Inorganic)

P3 = 600 kg/ha cow manure.

P4 = 600 kg/ha cow manure and bio-organic AcCKB20 - P24 600 kg/ha.

P5 = 600 kg/ha cow manure and bio-organic AcCKB4 - B28 600 kg/ha.

P6 = 600 kg/ha cow manure and bio-organic AcCKW5 - P24 600 kg/ha.

P7 = cow manure 600 kg/ha, bio-organic 600 kg/ha, and 5 mL probiotic AcCKB20 - P24/plant

P8 = cow manure 600 kg/ha, bio-organic AcCKB4 - B28 600 kg/ha, and 5 mL of AcCKB4 - B28 probiotic solution/plant.

P9 = cow manure 600 kg/ha, bio-organic AcCKW5 - P24 600 kg/ha, and 5 mL probiotic solution AcCKW5 - P24/plant

Bio-organic is made from cow manure incubated with selected probiotics. 500 mL of probiotics was sprayed on 150 kg of cow manure then stirred evenly and incubated for 14 days. During the incubation period, stirring is done every 2-3 days so that the probiotic bacteria can develop evenly. After 14 days of incubation, the bio-organic is then used as a probiotic carrier. Soil tillage was carried out perfectly (maximum tillage) then 27 plots were made measuring 400 cm x 550 cm. After tillage and making experimental plots, the land was incubated for a week and sprayed with herbicides. Four to five days after spraying herbicides, manure and bio-organic fertilizers are applied according to treatment and left for three days before planting. Planting using a double row pattern, spacing of 50 cm x 50 cm x 100 cm wherein each hole 2 seeds are planted. In each experimental plot, there were 56 planting holes (population $25,454 \text{ plants ha}^{-1}$). Seeds are sown on the same day. 5 plants were also planted for each treatment in polybags as samples of destructive plants for observation of vegetative growth and growth analysis (relative growth rate and leaf area index). There are nine treatments which are divided into five types of implementation, namely:

P1: The seeds are planted directly, and no fertilization is applied, either NPK fertilizer, cow manure, or bio-organic,

P2: 40% NPK fertilizer was applied a week after planting, and 60% was applied eight weeks after planting,

P3: 100% manure is given three days before planting

P4, P5, and P6: tree types of Bio-organic given three days before planting

P7, P8, and P9: Cow manure and tree types of Bio-organic were given three days before planting and continued with 5 mL of probiotic solution at the age of one month after planting.

Observations made include analysis of soil and bio-organic fertilizers, plant growth and analysis of plant growth, yield components, and production

Analysis of soil, organic fertilizer, and bio-organic fertilizer

Soil analysis was carried out before and after planting, while analysis of organic and bio-organic fertilizers was carried out after 14 days of probiotic incubation on cow manure. Soil analysis before planting was carried out to determine the soil type and nutrient content, while soil analysis after planting was carried out to obtain information on whether there was a change (soil type and nutrient content) after fertilization was given.

Plant growth

Plant growth observed included vegetative and generative growth. For the vegetative component, the observed variables included plant height, number of branches, and number of leaves, while for the generative component the variables observed were flowering age, harvest age, and harvest period. Observations of vegetative growth were carried out when the plants had perfect leaves (trifoliate) which were around the third week until the plants entered the generative phase at the eighth week (inflorescence release). Generative growth observations were carried out when the plants began to flower until the end of harvest. Observations and measurements of plant height, number of branches, and number of leaves were carried out 60 days after planting, while observations of flowering age were carried out when plants in one experimental unit had flowered >50%, and harvesting age was calculated based on the average length of time needed from planting to the first harvest plants from each treatment. The harvest period was calculated from the first harvest to the last harvest.

Plant growth analysis

In this study, the growth analysis carried out was the analysis of the leaf area index and the relative growth rate of plants. Growth analysis used destructive samples which were observed periodically every seven days. Sampling was carried out when the plants had perfect leaves (trifoliate leaves). The Observations were made seven times to the relative growth rate (RGR) using destructive samples, namely by observing the dry weight of the plant periodically for seven observations. The Observations were made from the second week to the eighth week by drying plant samples at 70°C for 3 x 24 hours. The difference in the dry weight of the plants in the interval of the observation period is the value of the relative growth rate. With seven observations produced six values of the relative growth rate of plants. The relative growth rate is calculated by the equation:

$RGR = (\ln BK2 - \ln BK1) / (T2 - T1)$, where :

BK is the dry weight of the plant and T is the time of observation

The leaf area of the sword bean was obtained from the multiplication of leaf length, leaf width, and the constant 2,1774 according to Sutoro and Manik (2014), while the total leaf area (TLA) was obtained from the multiplication of leaf area and the number of leaves per plant. Furthermore, the leaf area index is generated from the distribution of the total leaf area to the land area per plant (LHt) or ground total (GA).

$LAI = TLA / (LHt \text{ or } GA)$, where TLA is the result of multiplying leaf area (LA) by the number of leaves per plant while LHt is land area per plant or ground area (GA) per plant.

Yield component

The yield component is the potential of the plant's ability to produce optimum productivity. The yield components of the sword bean plant include the number of inflorescences per plant, the total number of pods per plant, the number of pithy pods per plant, the number of harvested pods, the number of rotten pods, empty and fallen pods, the number of young pods, pod length, and the number of seeds per pod (Sarijan *et al.*, 2018).

Production

Production is defined as the yield of jack beans per unit area of land. Production is strongly influenced by plant growth in both the vegetative and generative phases. A good growth phase will produce a good yield component and is expected to result in high production.

Data analysis

The observed data were then processed by analysis of variance using Excel 2007 software in a randomized block design (RBD) with three replications. If there is a significant effect, a further test carried out using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at level of 5%.

Results and discussion

Soil and microbes analysis

The soil type of the research area is Dusty Clay Loam. The results of soil chemical analysis before planting: low organic C, moderate total N, low C/N, acid H₂O pH, very high P₂O₅ HCL, low K₂O HCL, very low Bray 1 P₂O₅, moderate Ca, medium Mg, low K, Very low Na, high CEC and low base saturation. In general, the fertility status of the land used is low (Table 1).

The results of the chemical analysis showed that the organic fertilizer used was alkaline with very high total C-organic and N content, moderate C/N content, and very low P₂O₅ content. After incubation with three pairs of probiotics for 14 days, a decomposition process of organic matter occurred which caused an increase in water content, and a decrease in C-organic and total N but did not change the classification of chemical properties. P₂O₅ content also tends to decrease (Table 2).

Microbial analysis on the soil, organic and bio-organic fertilizers showed that *Pseudomonas* sp and *Actinomyces* sp bacteria were present in the soil, and *Bacillus* sp, was not detected. In organic fertilizers, three types of bacteria were detected in a certain number of colonies. In bio-organic with probiotic pairs AcCKB20 - P24, AcCKB4 - B28, and AcCKW5 - P24, all were detected by the number of colonies as presented in Table 3.

Vegetative growth

The results of the variance analysis showed that in the observation of vegetative growth, the treatment did not affect plant height, the number of branches, and the number of leaves of the sword bean (Table 4).

The data in Table 4 shows that the plant height, number of branches, and the lowest number of leaves resulted from the treatment without fertilization followed by the manure treatment, while the NPK fertilizer treatment and the use of bio-organic fertilizer tended to produce better vegetative growth. Plants that are given bio-organic fertilizers accompanied by watering with microbial solution tend to produce taller plants and have more leaves. Soil analysis (Table 1) shows that soil fertility is low. This is thought to be the cause of the low plant height, number of branches, and number of leaves even though statistically there was no difference between plants that were not fertilized and fertilized. The research results of Firmansyah *et al.* (2017) showed that the treatment of NPK fertilizer doses on eggplant plants began to have an effect from 60 DAP on plant height, number of productive branches, number of leaves, and stem diameter. Data, as presented in Table 4, shows a tendency for plants to produce different heights if the observation period is extended due availability of different nutrients. In this study, the observation of vegetative growth was limited to avoid flower loss during observation and measurement because the plant had entered the generative growth phase.

Generative growth

The results of the variance analysis showed that the treatment had an effect on the harvest period and had no effect on the flowering and harvesting ages (Table 5). The flowering and harvest age of unfertilized plants tend to be slower, but the harvest period is faster. Plants that were given manure and bio-organic and watered with the same bio-organic solution (M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24-prob solution) had a faster harvest age and a longer harvest period but were not different from the NPK fertilizer treatment. M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28, M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24, M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24-prob solution, M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28-probiotic solution.

Jack beans are classified as indeterminate plants so the slower the plants start to be harvest with a short harvest period, the products produced will be lower when compared to plants that start to be harvested earlier and have a longer harvest period.

Plant growth is related to the availability of nutrients. If the plant nutrition is sufficient, the plant will grow and produce optimally. In the soil are general there is a source of nutrients for plants., but the nutrients are not necessarily available and sufficient. Characteristics of nutrient-deficient plants can be identified through visible symptoms, for example on leaves such as chlorosis, necrosis, and accumulation of anthocyanins that

produce red, blue, and purple colors on the leaves, stunted plants, and reduced new growth on shoots and leaves (Azzamy 2016). Adequate plant nutrition will facilitate translocation through roots to plant parts, including flower formation, seed filling, and pod development.

Plant growth analysis

Plant growth analysis includes are leaf area index (LAI) and relative growth rate analysis (RGR). LAI analysis was based on leaf length, leaf width, the number of leaves, and land area as well as constant values (Sutoro and Mamik, 2014), while RGR was analyzed based on leaf dry weight periodically. The results of the LAI and RGR analysis are presented in Table 6.

The application of NPK fertilizer tends to produce a higher leaf area index, while unfertilized plants tend to have a lower leaf area index. The relative growth rate of plants fluctuated for all treatments with relatively the same results. The leaf area index reflects the amount of light intercepted by plants. The results of Sumarsono's research (2008) showed that the leaf area index of soybean plants still increased in line with the increasing age of the plant up to 8 weeks after planting, while the relative growth rate gave fluctuating results in each observation period. Leaf area index at a certain level can play an effectively role in producing producing photosynthate, but a small or even too large leaf area index is not effective as a photosynthetic organ. A large of leaf area index indicates the thickness of the leaf coating above the land surface where the thicker the land surface coating by the leaves will inhibit the entry of sunlight so that the function of the leaves as photosynthetic organs will not play a maximum role, even tend to be users of photosynthetic products. According to Siswadi and Dewi (2015) a certain extent, urea fertilizer has a different effect on the number of arrowroot leaves compared to biological and control fertilizers. Doses of urea fertilizer that are too high or too low tend to produce leaf area that is no different from the use of biological or control fertilizers.

Yield component

The yield component consisted of the number of inflorescences per plant, total pods per plant, pithy pods per plant, harvested pods, rotten pods, empty and fallen pods, young pods, pod length, and the number of seeds per pod. Yield component observation data are presented in Tables 7 and 8.

The results of the variance analysis showed that the application of NPK and bio-organic fertilizers affected the total number of pods per plant and the number of harvested pods per plant but had no effect on the number of inflorescences per plant (Table 7).

The results in Table 8 show that the application of NPK and bio-organic fertilizers had an effective on the number of fallen pods, empty pods, and rotten pods, the number of young pods, and pod length but had no effect on the number of seeds/pods.

The use of NPK fertilizer, although it gave a higher yield component, was not different from bio-organic, even though some components of bio-organic observations gave better yields. The use of NPK fertilizer gave the highest are yields of a number of pods per inflorescent, number of pods per plant, number of young pods, and together with manure and bio-organic (AcCKW5-P24) treatment with bio-organic watering resulted in longer pods than others. Treatment without fertilization resulted in the lowest component of crop yields for all observations.

The data in Tables 7 and 8 show that the treatment has not been able to increase the number of harvested pods. From an average of 31.7 pods produced by the crop, only 10.9 pods were successfully harvested, 11.9 pods were deciduous, empty pods, and rotten pods, and 8.9 young pods were still present. The number of harvested pods may still increase if the harvest period is extended so that the young pods can mature for harvesting. The presence of young pods at the end of the harvest was related to the indeterminate nature of the sword bean plant. Flowers and pods are still growing where the earlier pods have been harvested, while the harvest period for the sword pods can reach 9 to 12 months (Kasno 2015).

Production

Observations on the production of jack beans include the seeds production per plot (kg) and production per hectare (tons). Data on crop production per plot and per ha are presented in Table 9.

The results of the variance analysis showed that the treatment had a significant effect on the production variable of sword koro beans. The results of the DMRT test showed that the highest production resulted from the NPK fertilization treatment, but its results were not different from the treatment of cow manure + bio-organic AcCKB20 - P24 + probiotic solution AcCKB20 - P24. The highest production/plot was 7,7 kg (NPK and cow manure fertilization, bio AcCKB20 - P24+ solution and the lowest was 3,9 kg (without fertilizer). The highest production/ha was 3,51 tons (NPK fertilization), and the lowest was 1,76 tons (without fertilizer). The results of Karo et al., 2021's research concerning the application of liquid organic fertilizer to jack bean plants obtained results that did not affect observations of vegetative growth but did affect plant yields. Furthermore, Soedarjo (2021) applied 5 tons/ha of sheep manure to the jack bean plant and was able to produce 6.69 tons/ha of jack bean seed production.

Conclusion

Fertilization affects the yield and production components but has not been able to increase the number of harvested pods (production) of sword beans.

The treatment of bio-organic and probiotics causes changes in soil aggregates but does not cause changes in soil classification. Bio-organic can increase the chemical content of the soil, except for the decreased cation exchange capacity.

The application of probiotic microbes starting with organic fertilizers and then bio-organic fertilizers and giving probiotic microbial solutions resulted in growth and production that were relatively the same as the use of inorganic fertilizers.

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Table 1 Soil texture and soil chemical content before planting

Texture and chemical properties	rate	Unit	Information
Tekstur			
`- Sand	8	%	Dusty Clay Loam
`- Dusty	67	%	
`- Clay	25	%	
C-Organik	1.87	%	Low
N-total	0.22	%	Medium
C/N	9		Low
pH H ₂ O	5		Sour
P ₂ O ₅ HCL (Total)	102	me/100g	Very high
K ₂ O HCL	13	me/100g	Low
P ₂ O ₅ Bray 1 (Available)	8	Ppm	Very low
Cation Exchange Rate			
`- Ca	5.72		Medium
`- Mg	1.35		Medium
`- K	0.12		Low
`- Na	.0,05		Very low
`- KTK	29.84	me/100g	High
KATION Free (KB)	24	%	Low

Description: primary data, results of laboratory analysis

Table 2 Chemical content of organic and bio-organic fertilizers

Parameter uji	Organic Fertilizer (1) and Bio-Organik Fertilizer (2 s/d 4)							
	Organic fertilizer		AcCKB20 - P24		AcCKB4 - B28		AcCKW5 - P24	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)				
	rate (%)	Unit	rate(%)	unit	rate (%)	Unit	rate (%)	unit
pH H ₂ O	8.1	Basa	8.1	basa	8.1	Basa	7.9	Basa
Water content	62.86	-	72.80	-	70.03	-	70.91	-
C-organic	12	Vh	8.54	Vh	9.24	Vh	8.46	Vh
N-total	0.91	Vh	0.80	Vh	1	Vh	0.88	Vh
C/N Ratio	13.2	Md	11	Md	9	L	10	L
P ₂ O ₅ -total	0.58	VI	0.47	VI	0.53	VI	0.59	VI
P ₂ O ₅ -available	0.42	VI	0.31	VI	0.33	VI	0.40	VII

Note: primary data, results of laboratory analysis.

Fh : Very high, Md : Mediaum,

L:: Low, Vr : very low

Table 3 Analysis of functional microbes in soil, organic and bio-organic fertilizers (CFU/g)

Parameter analisis	Soil	Organic Fertilizer	Bio-Organik Fertilizer		
			AcCKB20 vs P24	AcCKB4 vs B28	AcCKW5 vs P24
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp	2.88 x 10 ⁸	1.37 x 10 ⁸	1.70 x 10 ⁸	not on analyze	2.29 x 10 ⁸
<i>Bacillus</i> sp	aren't detection	3.30 x 10 ³	not on analyze	2.20 x 10 ³	not on analyze
<i>Actinomycetes</i> sp	6.20 x 10 ²	1.80 x 10 ⁴	4.80 x 10 ³	1.30 x 10 ⁴	1.23 x 10 ⁴

Note: primary data, results of laboratory analysis.

CFU/g = Colony Forming Unit/grams

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Table 4 Plant height, number of branches, and number of leaves of jack bean curd 60 days after planting (DAP).

Treatment	Plant heigh (cm)	Branches	Leaves
No fertilization	116.7	5.7	7.9
NPK Fertilizer	139.7	6.5	9.5
Cow Manure	128.8	5.8	8.5
M-Bio-AcCKB20 vs P24	143.4	6.1	9.3
M-Bio-AcCKB4 vs B28	137.3	6.2	9.2
M-Bio-AcCKW5 vs P24	144.4	6.2	9.1
M-Bio-AcCKB20 vs P24-sol prob	147.7	6.3	9.5
M-Bio-AcCKB4 vs B28-sol prob	150.2	6.3	9.4
M-Bio-AcCKW5 vs P24-sol prob)	151.1	6.2	9.5
Mean	139.9	6.1	9.1
Coefficient of diversity	18.8	4.7	9.7

Table 5 Flowering age, harvesting age and harvesting period of jack beans at various fertilization treatments.

Treatment	Generative character		
	Flowering age (day)	Harvest age (day)	Harvest period (day)
No fertilization	55.4	140.3	35.5 b
NPK Fertilizer	55.0	134.5	38.7 a
Cow Manure	55.0	139.8	35.7 b
M-Bio-AcCKB20 vs P24	55.0	139.6	36.0 b
M-Bio-AcCKB4 vs B28	55.1	139.4	37.7 a
M-Bio-AcCKW5 vs P24	55.0	140.0	37.1 ab
M-Bio-AcCKB20 vs P24-sol prob	55.1	136.5	38.5 a
M-Bio-AcCKB4 vs B28-sol prob	55.1	134.7	38.0 a
M-Bio-AcCKW5 vs P24-sol prob)	55.2	133.3	38.4 a
Mean	55.1	137.6	37.4
coefficient of diversity	0.7	2.9	1.8

Note: numbers followed by the same letter in the same colum are not different in the 5% DMRT test

Table 6 Leaf area index (LAI) and relative growth rate (RGR) of jack beans.

Treatment	Leaf Area Index	Relative Growth Rate
No fertilization	2.5	0.05
NPK Fertilizer	4.0	0.04
Cow Manure	2.8	0.05
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24	3.5	0.05
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28	3.5	0.05
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24	3.6	0.05
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24-sol prob	3.7	0.05
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28-sol prob	3.7	0.05
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24-sol prob)	3.8	0.04
Mean	3.5	0.05

Table 7 Number of inflorescences/plants (NIp), total number of pods/plants (NPp), number of pithy pods/plants (NPPp) and number of harvested pods/plants (NHPP)

Treatment	Yield Component			
	NIp	NPp	NPPp	NHPP
No fertilization	39.9	26.7 d	22.1 e	9.6 d
NPK Fertilizer	43.3	34.0 a	28.4 abc	11.9 a
Cow Manure	41.5	29.3 c	25.3 d	9.8 cd
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24	42.7	32.4 ab	27.5 bcd	10.8 abcd
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28	43.4	31.0 bc	26.5 bcd	11.0 abc
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24	40.8	30.8 bc	25.9 cd	10.4 bcd
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24-sol prob	42.6	33.4 a	28.8 ab	11.8 a
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28-sol prob	45.1	33.3 a	28.6 abc	11.6 ab
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24-sol prob)	43.7	34.0 a	30.3 a	11.5 ab
Mean	42.6	31.7	27.0	10.9

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Coefficient of diversity	4.5	3.7	4.8	6.0
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Note: numbers followed by the same letter in the same column are not different in the 5% DMRT test

Table 8 Number of deciduous, empty and rotten pods (NDERp), number of young pods (NEp), pod length (Lp), and number of seeds/pods (NSp) of the jack bean plant

Treatment	Component of Yield			
	NDERp (pods)	NEp (pods)	Lp (cm)	NSp (seed)
No fertilization	9.2 c	7.9 cd	24.8 c	7.3
NPK Fertilizer	11.8 ab	10.3 a	27.1 ab	9.0
Cow Manure	12.2 ab	7.4 d	26.4 b	8.7
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24	12.9 a	8.7 abcd	26.4 b	8.7
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28	12.0 ab	7.9 cd	27.1 ab	9.0
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24	12.0 ab	8.3 bcd	26.9 ab	8.7
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24-sol prob	11.7 b	9.8 ab	27.5 a	9.0
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28-sol prob	12.4 ab	9.4 abc	27.0 ab	9.0
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24-sol prob)	12.5 a	10.0 ab	27.5 a	9.3
Mean	11.9	8.9	26.8	8.7
Coefficient of diversity	8.1	11.6	2.3	7.6

Note: numbers followed by the same letter in the same column are not different in the 5% DMRT test

Table 9 Production (per plot and per hectare) of jack bean seeds in various fertilization treatments

Treatment	Production/plot	Production/hectare
	(kg)	(ton)
No fertilization	3.9 e	1.76 e
NPK Fertilizer	7.7 a	3.51 a
Cow Manure	5.3 d	2.40 d
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24	6.1 c	2.76 bc
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28	5. cd	2.60 cd
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24	6.0 c	2.75 c
M-Bio-AcCKB20 - P24-sol prob	7.7 a	3.49 a
M-Bio-AcCKB4 - B28-sol prob	6.9 b	3.13 b
M-Bio-AcCKW5 - P24-sol prob)	6.9 b	3.13 b
Mean	6.2	2.8
Coefficient of diversity	13.0	5.0

Note: numbers followed by the same letter in the same column are not different in the 5% DMRT test